

IMPROVING THE TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL TRAINING OF FEMALE WRESTLERS AT THE TRAINING STAGE

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Annotation: This thesis provides practical recommendations aimed at improving the technical and tactical training of female wrestlers during the training stage.

Keywords: Technical training, tactical training, wrestler, planning

Relevance

Significant efforts are being made to popularize, develop, and promote Kurash, our national sport that embodies ancient values such as bravery, courage, and patriotism, and to present it as a cultural treasure to the world. As is well known, Kurash is a sport rich in motor activity and has been passed down as a legacy from our ancestors.

The increasing popularity of Kurash has led to the organization of prestigious international competitions, modernization of material and technical facilities, improvement in the provision of sports equipment and uniforms, and expansion of production capabilities. There is also a growing focus on training qualified specialists, coaches, and staff in this field. The importance of this is underscored by a number of presidential decrees and decisions concerning the development of Kurash, particularly the Presidential Decree No. PQ-450 dated December 20, 2024, “On Measures to Take the Development and Popularization of the National Sport Kurash to a New Stage.” This document emphasizes the need to scientifically organize training sessions, which is one of today’s most urgent tasks.

The increasing level of competition in international Kurash tournaments necessitates improvements in the system of training athletes and coaches. The

training of qualified female wrestlers and coaches is a long-term pedagogical process that requires step-by-step optimal planning of sports training.

In Uzbekistan, great attention is being given to the development and popularization of Kurash, expanding public participation, turning Kurash into a mass sport, and striving for its inclusion in the program of the International Olympic Games. Identifying talented and promising athletes and coaches and directing them toward long-term training programs are among the priority goals.

Currently, there are several methods used to assess physical fitness and plan training loads for athletes (L.R. Ayrapetyants, 1992; Y.V. Verkhoshansky, 1993; F.A. Kerimov, 1995; R.M. Matkarimov, 1999; V.N. Platonov, 2004; R.D. Khalmukhamedov, 2010; M.N. Umarov, 2011).

Experts in combat sports in our country — F.A. Kerimov (1995), A.N. Abdiev (1997), R.M. Matkarimov (1999), V.N. Shin (2001), F.M. Polatov (2002), Kh.R. Akhmedov (2005), A.A. Ruziev (2004), B.D. Berdikulov (2004), K. Yusupov (2005), N.N. Azizov (2007), Z.A. Bakiyev (2009), F.Yu. Bagdasarov (2010), S.U. Kupalov (2011) — emphasize the importance of improving the technical-tactical training of wrestlers and of purposefully planning and monitoring the training process to identify effective methods.

Conclusion

Effective training of female wrestlers involves planning and managing the training process, assessing the level of physical and technical-tactical readiness, shaping sports results, and controlling pre-competition preparation and performance during competitions. However, such methods have not yet been fully applied in the training of female Kurash wrestlers.

Currently, the most effective approach in training female wrestlers involves the use of one-sided dominant load orientations in training sessions. In preparing qualified female wrestlers and coaches, improving the technical and tactical training process is of great significance.

Integrating theoretical preparation along with technical-tactical and physical training in the training process, and organizing training sessions based on scientific

principles, increases the efficiency of these sessions. This allows specialists in physical education and sports to better contribute to preparing skilled athletes and coaches capable of raising the nation's flag higher on the international stage.

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